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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D4.2 Interim Report on Education in Standardisation

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Nature of the deliverable:		R
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)	
EU-RES	Classified Information: RESTREINT UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-CO N	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is part of Work Package 4 “Standards Academy Programme of the StandICT.eu 2026 project. This is an interim version and will be updated by the end of the project. A progress update on the development of educational initiatives related to ICT standardisation as outlined by the WP4 following the creation of the International Directory on Education about Standardisation (IdEAS) established by Task 4.1 is provided.

The report outlines the establishment of the EUOS Standards Education Group (EUOS-SEG), a panel of ICT standardisation education experts. This group manages the development and delivery of the EUOS Academy content, consisting of a series of informative lectures designed to broaden knowledge of ICT standardisation.

Furthermore, a section dedicated to the initiatives for education standardisation describes the training and education courses that have taken place with the aim of distributing content and insights about standard education. This section includes a short description of the nine webinars that were carried out. The topics of these webinars range from SME’s involvement in standardisation, the geopolitics of standardisation, research and open source topics and their intersection with standards and the new standard-essential patents (SEP) regulation.

Considering the increased emphasis the project has on involving SMEs in standardisation, a dedicated section of the report addresses initiatives to include and increase SMEs' participation in standardisation topics. These initiatives include SME leadership Skills workshops, StandICT.eu2026 Training Modules, and the SME Mentorship Programme.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction	9
2. EUOS Standards Education Group	10
3. Initiatives for Education Standardisation	11
3.1 Teaching Module Development	11
3.1.1 Teaching Material	11
3.2 Main Webinars Illustration	12
3.2.1 EUOS Standards Academy: Towards The Future Of Education On Standardisation	12
3.2.2 Standards Academy Workshop: Developing Leadership Capacity for SMEs in European and International Standardisation Organisations	14
3.2.3 Standards Academy Webinar: Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation	15
3.2.4 Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes?	17
3.2.5 ICT Standardisation Landscape	18
3.2.6 Interaction between Standardisation and Research	19
3.2.7 Training Webinar: Open Source and Standardisation	20
3.2.8 Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation: Focus on India	21
3.2.9 EUOS Training Webinar: Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey	22
3.2.10 Standard Essential Patents Regulation	24
3.3 Outcomes from Webinars	25
4. Initiatives for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)	27
5. Action Plan and Next Steps	29

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1 - EUOS Standards Academy: Towards the future of education on standardisation (June 2023)	14
Figure 2 - Standards Academy Workshop: Developing leadership capacity for SMEs in European and international standardisation (November 2023)	15
Figure 3 - Standards Academy Webinar: Geopolitics of ICT standardisation (January 2024)	17
Figure 4 - Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes? (February 2024)	18
Figure 5 - ICT Standardisation Landscape (February 2024)	19
Figure 6 - Interaction between Standardisation and Research (March 2024)	20
Figure 7 - Training Webinar: Open Source and Standardisation (March 2024)	21
Figure 8 - Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation: Focus on India (May 2024)	22
Figure 9 - EUOS Training Webinar: Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey (May 2024)	24
Figure 10 - Standard Essential Patents Regulation (June 2024)	25

ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
DSME	European Digital SME Alliance
EAG	External Advisory Group
EARTO	European Association of Research and Technology Organisations
EPO	European Patent Office
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUIPO	European Union Intellectual Property Office
EUOS	EU Observatory for ICT Standardisation
EUOS-SEG	EUOS Standards Education Group
EURAS	European Academy for Standardisation
FOREST	Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards
HEI	Higher Education Institution
HLF	High-Level Forum on Standardisation
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
idEaS	International Directory on Education about Standardisation
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IEEE SA	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standards Association
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
NSAI	National Standards Authority of Ireland
OFE	Open Forum Europe
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
R&I	Research & Innovation
RAN	Radio Access Network
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SBS	Small Business Standards
SC	Standards Committee
SDO	Standard Development Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
STAIR	Standards, Innovation & Research
STS	Standardisation Training Strategy
TC	Technical Committee
TWG	Technical Working Groups
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

StandICT.eu 2026 is a European initiative supporting the EU's engagement in international ICT standardisation. For the 2026 edition, the focus is to strengthen the global reach of the European ICT Standardisation Ecosystem. This will be achieved through fellowship programmes, the creation of the EUOS Academy, training, Technical Working Groups (TWG), Expert Groups, and the Forum on EU Strategy for ICT Standards (FOREST).

The StandICT.eu project established the EUOS Academy tasked with developing educational and training resources to enhance understanding of the ICT standardisation process and ICT standards, but also the performance of webinars.

The EUOS Academy's crucial role in advancing and professionalising the education about ICT standardisation relies on current education material, but also relevant research outputs within the field of ICT standardisation. To ensure the effectiveness of these efforts, the Academy benefits from the guidance and expertise of a dedicated group responsible for managing the creation and delivery of its educational initiatives.

The WP delivers a comprehensive education strategy, material and webinars to cater for all of the stakeholders:

- Improve the skills and knowledge in ICT standardisation strategy of experts of EU organisations involved in international ICT standardisation;
- Develop target group-specific training material, modules and SME mentorship programme;
- Perform large-scale training through webinars for different levels of standardisation skills.

D4.2's main objective is to present the current status and activities under the StandICT2026 Training Academy until the end of June 2024.

2. EUOS STANDARDS EDUCATION GROUP

Based on the Academy Group of StandICT 2023, the EUOS Standards Education Group (EUOS-SEG) was created to accompany the strategy and actions developed under Task 4.1's Standards Academy. This group follows the developing and delivering the EUOS Academy Series, which consists of informative lectures designed to broaden the understanding of ICT standardisation.

The EUOS-SEG comprises a distinguished panel of experts in ICT standardisation. These individuals possess a wide range of experience and draw from various backgrounds, including academia, industry, and SDOs. So far, the group has gathered online on four occasions.

- Meeting #1 05. September 2023
- Meeting #2 05. December 2023
- Meeting #3 27. March 2024
- Meeting #4 10. July 2024 scheduled

Professor Ivana Mijatovic, a pillar of the Faculty of Organisational Sciences at the University of Belgrade, leads this team as chair. The co-chair complements her expertise, Knut Blind, the Coordinator of Business Unit Innovation and Regulation at the Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI.

The following table presents the membership of the 13 experts who are actively involved in the EUOS-SEG.

Name	Contribution	Organisation
Ivana Mijatovic	CHAIR	University of Belgrade
Knut Blind	CO-CHAIR	FHG
Harshvardhan Pandit	Member	Dublin City University
Brian McAuliffe	Member	HP
Anna Gallet	Member	ISO
Ian Gardner	Member	IEC
Claire d'Esclercs	Member	ETSI
Sandra Drechsler	Member	VDMA
Paul Killeen	Member	EC
David Phillip	Member	JTC1
Maria Ines Robles	Member	Internet Engineering Task Force
Nicolas Domenjoud	Member	ILNAS
Andrea D'Aquino	Member	IFAG CP PP

3. INITIATIVES FOR EDUCATION STANDARDISATION

As part of the Standards Academy Programme, StandICT.eu develops Training and Education Courses for Standards Education, fostering a solid foundation for ICT standardisation by creating a multifaceted program encompassing various learning activities.

3.1 Teaching Module Development

Using the strategy developed under Task 4.1 and documented in D4.1 as a foundation, Task 4.2 states that StandICT.eu develops Training and Education Courses for Standards Education. This involves setting up the EUOS-SEG to accompany the creation and delivery of the EUOS Academy Series of ICT Standards Lectures. The content considers [previous work from StandICT.eu 2023](#) about standardisation and materials by national, EU, and international standardisation bodies.

After the finalisation of the Standardisation Training Strategy (STS) of StandICT2026 with the submission of D4.1, it was presented to and discussed with the EUOS Standards Education Group (SEG) chaired by Ivana Mijatovic to collect feedback and modify or expand it, if needed.

3.1.1 TEACHING MATERIAL

Existing teaching material from the previous edition of StandICT.eu, documented in D4.5 of StandICT.2023, including previous webinars, was screened and considered to be used as input for developing the six modules. Most relevant is the update of the textbook published by ETSI (Abdelkafi et al. 2021) because it is focused on ICT standardisation and the most recently published source. However, the comprehensive and detailed [material](#) presented and provided by HSBooster.eu was also considered. The content of the modules was presented and discussed with the SEG.

The six modules cover the following topics:

The two [basic](#) models focus, on the one hand, on the general role of standards in ICT and, on the other hand, on the ICT standardisation landscape.

The two [intermediate](#) modules cover the linkages between research, innovation and standardisation in ICT in general, and Intellectual Property Rights, particularly patents, and standardisation in ICT.

Finally, the two [advanced](#) courses address the complex relation between standardisation and open source and finally ICT standardisation in the context of geopolitics (technological sovereignty).

The material on ICT standardisation and open source is currently being reviewed by an open source expert. The powerpoint slides on ICT standardisation in the context of geopolitics or better technological sovereignty are already available. The summary will be released when the copyright related to a forthcoming journal publication is settled. The material on the intermediate module on IPR and ICT standardisation will be released after the webinar on the regulation of standard-essential patents has been performed on June 27 2024.

Further topics could be technology specific lectures (AI, blockchain, etc) to generate synergies with other projects (e.g. SEEBLOCKS.eu), but also the role of ICT standardisation for start-ups.

The webinars are based on PDFs of PowerPoint slides plus a short synopsis of three to five pages, including links and references. Please find here the current status of the teaching material [here](#).

3.2 Main Webinars Illustration

Nine webinars and workshops were held as part of the dissemination activities. Below is a concise summary of the content covered in each event.

3.2.1 EUOS STANDARDS ACADEMY: TOWARDS THE FUTURE OF EDUCATION ON STANDARDISATION

On June 13th 2023, [the webinar](#), officially presenting the launch of the StandICT.eu 2026 Academy, also addressed the increasing need to standardise education and knowledge in HEI curricula and its impact on economic growth, the "European Green Deal," the "New Industrial Strategy for Europe," and the Sustainable Development Goals. The EU-funded projects StandICT.eu and HSbooster.eu are working to close this gap on different levels, strategically relevant for European society and EU global leadership. To translate its objectives into action, the consortium established and managed the EUOS Standards Academy.

During this event, gratitude was expressed to Brian McAuliffe, the current chair and Director of Technology Standards at HP, for his exceptional work over the past three years leading the previous StandICT.eu Academy, as well as a warm welcome to Ivana Mijatovic, Professor at the Faculty of Organisational Sciences, University of Belgrade, as the new chair of the EUOS Standards Academy within StandICT.eu 2026.

A total of 47 people registered to attend the event, which was organised around five main sessions summarised below:

- Session 1, "Towards the Future of Education on Standardisation StandICT.eu EUOS Standards Academy," by Carlos López Rodríguez, Policy Officer ICT

Standardisation, provided a quick overview of the importance of standard education, some of the initiatives from the European Commission, the key challenges in standardisation education, and the strategic engagement from R&I in standards development.

- Session 2, “Making research results work for society—Commission Recommendation on Code of Practice on Standardisation,” by Gergely Tardos, Policy officer, focused on the critical actions for standardisation strategy, the objective of the Code of Practice on Standardisation, and the process of establishing the code. Additionally, he provided recommendations to each stakeholder group (HEI, project partners, and policy stakeholders).
- Session 3, “Training the Next Generation of ICT Standards Experts,” by Brian McAuliffe, Chair of the EUOS, provided an overview of the previous Standards Academy of StandICT2023, highlighting the differences or overlaps between StandICT Standards Academy and the HSBooster.eu.
- Session 4, “Bringing standardisation closer to researchers”, by Ivana Mijatovic - Chair of the EUOS Standards Academy in StandICT.eu 2026, explained the HSbooster.eu Training Academy objectives, target audience (researchers), structure and methodology. Furthermore, an introductory explanation of the Serious Smiley Game was provided.
- Session 5, “Standards Academy Strategy: First Ideas,” by Knut Blind, discussed ICT Standardisation, including the vision, mission, status quo, objectives (short, medium, and long term), and finally, the action plan and recommendations to achieve such goals.

StandICT.eu EUOS Standards Academy:
Towards the future of education on standardisation

SPEAKERS

 Brian McAuliffe Chair of the EUOS Standards Academy in StandICT.eu 2023 & Director of Technology Standards at HP		
 Gergely Tardos Policy Officer at Directorate General for Research and Innovation of European Commission		

13 June 2023
15.00 – 16.00 CEST

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hsbooster.eu | [@HSBoosterEU](https://twitter.com/HSBoosterEU) | [/company/hsbooster-eu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/hsbooster-eu)

Funded by the European Union

Figure 1 - EUOS Standards Academy: Towards the future of education on standardisation (June 2023)

3.2.2 STANDARDS ACADEMY WORKSHOP: DEVELOPING LEADERSHIP CAPACITY FOR SMEs

IN EUROPEAN AND INTERNATIONAL STANDARDISATION ORGANISATIONS

[This workshop](#) on 15th November 2023, directed explicitly at SMEs not yet directly involved in standardisation processes, strives to develop leadership competencies to lead working groups and technical committees in European and international standardisation organisations. For this purpose, two experimented Small Business Standards (SBS - the European organisation representing small and medium enterprises in the standardisation system) experts with leadership positions at ISO and CEN-CENELEC levels conducted the workshop and directly exchanged with the participants. Partners of the StandICT team will further outline the training possibilities and SME-targeted support activities offered by the project consortium. A total of 51 people registered to attend the webinar.

The key takeaways from the webinar include:

- How SMEs should actively participate in standardisation processes to gain competitive advantages, access knowledge, and influence market requirements and regulations.
- Some challenges SMEs face in participating with international standardisation bodies include resource limitations, diverse stakeholder interests, and geopolitical factors.
- SMEs are encouraged to engage with standardisation committees as they can benefit from the knowledge and expertise shared and stay informed about the latest industry trends, technologies, and best practices, leading to innovation and competitiveness.
- Considering how standardisation bodies increasingly address environmental sustainability will allow SMEs to align their practices with sustainable development goals, gain a competitive edge, and contribute to a greener future.
- Efforts should be made to bridge the gap between SMEs and standardisation bodies by creating platforms for collaboration, providing funding opportunities, and raising awareness about the benefits of participation.

Figure 2 - Standards Academy Workshop: Developing leadership capacity for SMEs in European and international standardisation (November 15, 2023)

3.2.3 STANDARDS ACADEMY WEBINAR: GEOPOLITICS OF ICT STANDARDISATION

[This webinar](#) on 29th January 2024 dived into the intricate world of ICT standardisation and its geopolitical implications, starting with a comprehensive exploration of technological sovereignty and the evolving roles of key global players in shaping the landscape of international standards. A total of 193 people registered to attend the webinar.

The speakers discussed various facets of ICT standardisation, from the geopolitics surrounding the Open Radio Access Network (RAN) to China's changing influence in global standard-setting. This webinar offered a valuable opportunity to gain insights into the power dynamics and cooperation within international ICT standards.

Four different sessions were included in the webinar, addressing the following topics:

- Session 1, “Intro into standardisation and geopolitics with a focus on technological sovereignty,” by Knut Blind (Fraunhofer ISI & TU Berlin), presented a conceptual model to discuss technological sovereignty and how standardisation can safeguard it. Moreover, it provided a list of policy recommendations and challenges to overcome.
- Session 2, “The power of standardisation” by Dirk Weiler (Nokia Head of Standards Policy). There were three main aspects covered: the importance of global standards, current challenges in the global standardisation system, and the consequences of geopolitical factors.
- Session 3, “The Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation: The Case of Open RAN” by Heejin Lee (Graduate School of International Studies, Yonsei

University, Republic of Korea). The focus of this session was open RAN, how it came to be, what it is and its applications and why it is important to standardisation and the geopolitical landscape.

- Session 4, “Cooperation and contestation: China’s evolving role in international standardisation,” by Daniel Fuchs (HU Berlin, BCCN), discussed how stakeholders from the Global North have an outsized influence on international standardisation, given their leadership positions in TCs, SCs, and WG, and how China’s industrial policy encouraged a rule-making approach and its domestic and international impact.

SPEAKERS

- Maria Giuffrida**
MODERATOR (Trust-IT Services, Italy)
- Knut Blind**
(Fraunhofer ISI & TU Berlin)
- Heejin Lee**
(Research Center for Digital Trade,
Graduate School of International Studies,
Yonsei University, Republic of Korea)
- Dirk Weiler**
(Nokia Head of Standards Policy)
- Daniel Fuchs**
(HU Berlin, BCCN)

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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

TRAINING WEBINAR
29th January 2024
16:00 - 18:00 (CET)

Geopolitics of ICT standardisation

In cooperation with

Berlin Contemporary China Network

Funded by the European Union

Figure 3 - Standards Academy Webinar: Geopolitics of ICT standardisation (January 31, 2024)

3.2.4 STANDARDISATION IN PRACTICE: WHEN IS THE RIGHT TIME FOR STANDARDISATION IN RESEARCH PROCESSES?

[The webinar](#) on 1st February 2024, organised in collaboration with HSBooster.eu discussed the importance of standardisation in research processes and the right time to implement it, with insights from experts in the field. It highlighted the role of standards in transferring innovation to the market, accessing financial resources, and increasing visibility. The different types of research and their relationship to standards were also explained. For this webinar, 48 people registered to participate in the event. The speakers for this event included:

- Ivana Mijatovic, HSbooster.eu Training Academy Lead, UoB
- Christian Goroncy, senior project manager DIN, the German Institute for Standardisation

- Knut Blind, Fraunhofer ISI & TU Berlin

The German Institute for Standardization (DIN) recognised the importance of supporting researchers. Their specialised research and transfer group, addressed this by assisting researchers in several ways, including securing funding, collaborating on research projects (through various roles like coordinator, partner, or subcontractor), and offering programs like DIN Connect and the Mobility Office. Additionally, FuT organised the Smart Cities Standards Forum, where the crucial link between standardisation and R&D was highlighted. By providing these resources and fostering connections, DIN empowers researchers to navigate the standardisation process and ultimately increase the impact of their work.

Furthermore, this webinar addressed the importance of standardisation in research, and participants contributed questionnaires to give an overview of how they implement standardisation in their research. Some key ideas from the webinar include:

- Standardisation is crucial for transferring innovation to the market, accessing financial resources, and increasing visibility.
- Different types of research (basic, applied, and experimental development) have varying relationships with standards.
- Standards play a role in defining terminology, ensuring compatibility, reducing variety, and providing information.

HSbooster.eu TRAINING ACADEMY
 standICT.eu 2026
 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

WEBINAR
 1 Feb 2024
 10:00 - 11:30 CET

Training Session ⑥
Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes?
 Register now!

Funded by the European Union

Figure 4 - Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes? (February 1, 2024)

3.2.5 ICT STANDARDISATION LANDSCAPE

The working group [Smart City and Smart Region](#) of the German IT industry association BITKOM invited Knut Blind to give a webinar on the ICT standardisation landscape. 30 participants attended this webinar on 14th February 2024. Knut Blind used the basic training material to give an overview of the ICT standardisation landscape. After an introduction, he presented the basics of standardisation, the various standards organisations of the ICT standardisation landscape and eventually the linkages between standard development organisations. The webinar ended with a brief discussion.

ICT Standardisation Landscape

ICT standardisation landscape

Knut Blind

Chair of the StandICT.eu Standards Academy

Head of the Business Unit Regulation and Innovation at Fraunhofer ISI

Chair of Innovation Economics at TU Berlin

Arbeitskreis Smart City / Smart Region

Webmeeting, Mittwoch, 14. Februar 2024, 15:00 – 17:30 Uhr

Standards und Interoperabilität in der Smart City

1

Figure 5 - ICT Standardisation Landscape (February 14, 2024)

3.2.6 INTERACTION BETWEEN STANDARDISATION AND RESEARCH

This seminar was organised on 12th March 2024 in Cologne by the German Research organisation DLR. More than 20 researchers attended the seminar.

After the presentation of current activities of the European Commission including StandICT, Knut Blind provided a definition of R&D, but then elaborated on the interlinkages between R&D and standardisation, and eventually the impacts of standards on research and innovation. The seminar ended with an intensive discussion of the presented topics.

Interaction between Standardisation and Research

Knut Blind
 Fraunhofer ISI & TU Berlin

Contribution of StandICT2026 to the second DLR Netzwerktreffen Normung

DLR Cologne, 12th of March 2024

Figure 6 - Interaction between Standardisation and Research (March 12, 2024)

3.2.7 TRAINING WEBINAR: OPEN SOURCE AND STANDARDISATION

[This webinar](#) on 18th March 2024 explored the critical link between open-source software and standardisation in the ICT world. It highlighted the need for both communities to collaborate and understand each other's perspectives. A total of 136 people registered to attend the webinar.

Some of the main takeaways from the webinar include:

- Open discussion and cooperation between open-source developers and standard-setting bodies are essential for progress.
- Bridging the gap between their different working styles and priorities can be challenging. However, collaboration is key to maximising their impact.
- New tools and approaches emerging in both communities present opportunities for collaboration and mutual benefit.
- Standards need to be flexible and accessible to all participants, fostering inclusivity and innovation.
- The webinar discussed the impact of EU regulations on open source and the need for a standardisation system that supports open source development.
- Closing the gap between open source and standardisation is crucial for fostering collaboration and driving innovation in ICT. By working together and adapting to new approaches, both communities can achieve shared goals and advance the future of technology.

SPEAKERS

- Knut Blind**
Fraunhofer ISI and TU Berlin
- Jory Burson**
The Linux Foundation
- Mirko Böhm**
Linux Foundation Europe
- Silona Bonewald**
Leadingbit Solutions | IEEE (Former)
- Daniel Haack**
DIN e.V. – Digital PlatForms
- Janosch Friedrich**

standICT.eu
 ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

ONLINE EVENT
18th March 2024
 16:00 - 18:00 (CET)

Open Source & Standardisation

JOIN US!

Figure 7 - Training Webinar: Open Source and Standardisation (March 18, 2024)

3.2.8 GEOPOLITICS OF ICT STANDARDISATION: FOCUS ON INDIA

[The webinar](#) on 27th May 2024 dived into the world of ICT standardisation in India, emphasising the importance of global collaboration, particularly between India and the EU. This collaboration can boost economic growth, trade, and international leadership in the digital landscape. However, aligning standards across diverse regulatory frameworks presents challenges. The session explored how to overcome these challenges and address technical trade barriers. Developing expertise in emerging technologies and ensuring market-relevant and adaptable standards are also crucial. A total of 74 people registered to attend the webinar.

Finally, the webinar highlighted the importance of raising awareness about the value of standards and encouraging their adoption across businesses, government, and civil society. Collaboration and harmonisation efforts are key to driving technological advancement, building trust in digital services, and ensuring global standards meet the needs of a diverse world.

Some of the key points emphasised by the webinar include:

- Standardised ICT systems are crucial for India's digital transformation and improved governance.
- Standardisation is moving towards specialised bodies, reflecting the growing complexity of technology.
- Open standards and interoperable systems are essential for building robust and connected digital infrastructure.
- India is developing its own standards in areas like identity, payments, and document sharing. Moreover, India's digital ecosystem architecture aims for interoperability and common digital platforms.
- India has the potential to contribute new standards, especially in areas with no existing global benchmarks. The strategy aims to build a comprehensive ecosystem, align with national policies, and elevate India's role in global standardisation efforts.

Figure 8 - Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation: Focus on India (May 27, 2024)

3.2.9 EUOS TRAINING WEBINAR: INSIGHTS FROM THE EUROPEAN STANDARDISATION PANEL SURVEY

The European Standardisation Panel conducted a Europe-wide survey to explore three key areas: identifying industry and stakeholder demand for potential standards arising from R&I projects; evaluating how EU R&I framework programs could effectively meet these needs; and emphasising the importance of standardisation as a mechanism for maximizing the value of research knowledge. The survey results indicated that policy initiatives, such as regulations and customer requirements (particularly for industry), alongside independent and collaborative research efforts undertaken by organisations, represent the most significant sources for driving the development of new standards.

The purpose of [this webinar](#) was to contextualise standardisation within the EU valorisation policy, an initiative of DG RTD of the European Commission. Additionally, the experts also discussed the role of research for standardisation in the European Standardisation Organisations, and presented the main results, recommendations and key insights and learnings from the HSBooster project. The webinar was divided into three main presentations with speakers from diverse backgrounds.

- “The role of standardisation for knowledge valorisation” by Gergely Tardos (EC DG RTD)
- “The role of research for standardisation at CEN/CENELEC” by Mian Livia (CEN/CENELEC)

- “Results and implications of the European Standardisation Panel” by Knut Blind (Fraunhofer ISI & TU Berlin)

Research and standardisation share a complex relationship; while research can both challenge and enhance existing standards, those standards can simultaneously support or hinder research.

When developing measurement and testing standards, the most crucial factor is incorporating research findings. This is followed by considerations of quality and environmental concerns. Research offers a significant advantage: free access to scientific content and the ability to seamlessly integrate the latest advancements as it becomes easier to keep track of scientific advancements. Based on this, recommendations are made for various stakeholders.

The key takeaways from the webinar include:

- More awareness and information are needed to integrate research results into standards to bridge the gap between research and standardisation processes.
- Adequate funding and support from policy and regulations are crucial to encourage companies to use research results for standardisation, ensuring the integration is sustainable and effective.
- Collaboration between industry and research organisations is essential to facilitate the integration process, as it brings together expertise from both sectors to drive innovation in standardisation.
- Standardisation training and education for researchers and industry professionals is necessary to enhance their understanding and involvement in the integration process, ultimately improving the quality of standards developed.

The banner features a dark blue vertical bar on the left with the text 'standICT.eu 2026' and 'ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe'. To the right is a light blue globe. At the top center is the 'EUOS Standards Academy' logo. A dark blue circle with a white globe icon is positioned below the bar. A dark blue pill-shaped box contains the date and time: '21 May 2024 14:00 – 16:00 CEST'. The main title 'Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey' is written in dark blue. A blue circle with white text says 'REGISTER NOW!'. At the bottom right is the 'Funded by the European Union' logo.

Figure 9 - EUOS Training Webinar: Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey (May 21, 2024)

3.2.10 STANDARD ESSENTIAL PATENTS REGULATION

After the European Parliament supported the EU Commission's proposal (COM(2023)0232) for a regulation on Standard Essential Patents (SEPs), the initiative has received broad support from stakeholders and academics for its potential to increase transparency, however, it also faces opposition from major SEP holders and other interested parties.

[The webinar](#) explored the developments related to the topic, discussed their implications, and answered questions about how these regulatory changes might impact businesses and the broader technology ecosystem.

The event was divided into three main sections. First, Emilio Davila-Gonzalez (DG Connect and StandICT Academy) and Knut Blind (Fraunhofer ISI) provided an introduction of StandICT. Afterwards, Anne von Zukowski (DG GROW) presented the SEP regulation followed by the intervention of multiple stakeholders from different companies such as Nokia, Continental, Audi, Linux Europe and Ericsson.

Figure 10 - Standard Essential Patents Regulation (June 27, 2024)

3.3 Outcomes from Webinars

The main objective of these webinars was to increase knowledge about ICT standardisation in general with a specific focus on Europe. Each addressed different topics and knowledge areas that should be considered to achieve the large-scale training they intended. While some highlighted the importance of EU leadership in standardisation and explored the efforts of StandICT.eu and other projects, they also discussed the current challenges and opportunities in

standardisation education. Moreover, they examined the impact of geopolitics on ICT standardisation and the evolving roles of global players.

The following table provides an overview of the registries for each webinar. A total of almost 800 hundred experts registered in all the events organised.

Webinar	Registrees
EUOS Standards Academy: Towards The Future Of Education On Standardisation	47
Standards Academy Workshop: Developing Leadership Capacity for SMEs in European and International Standardisation Organisations	51
Standards Academy Webinar: Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation	193
Standardisation in practice: When is the right time for standardisation in research processes?	48
ICT Standardisation Landscape	30
Interaction between Standardisation and Research	20
Training Webinar: Open Source and Standardisation	136
Geopolitics of ICT Standardisation: Focus on India	74
Insights from the European Standardisation Panel Survey	93
Standard Essential Patents Regulation	102
Total	794

Overall, these activities equip researchers, industry professionals, and students with the necessary knowledge and skills to contribute to developing and implementing ICT standards.

4. INITIATIVES FOR SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (SMEs)

StandICT.eu recognises the importance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) and their role in the ICT standardisation landscape. Even though these businesses represent 99% of businesses across the EU, they are often overlooked because they don't have the resources or knowledge to be involved. This poses severe inclusiveness issues and standard suitability. Because of this, SMEs are an essential target audience under StandICT2026's STS. Following the increased emphasis the project has on involving SMEs in standardisation, the webinars also provided training to SMEs on participating in standardisation processes and gaining leadership roles.

Standardisation knowledge shouldn't be limited to HEI, and training and informing people in the workplace is crucial, too. Moreover, skills development should include all company employees, not just IT specialists, especially in SMEs, as they often have fewer employees, and everyone must have a basic grasp of standardisation principles.

Some of the actions StandICT.eu has done to address this issue include:

- **SME leadership Skills workshops:** at the project's halfway course, DIGITAL SME organised one leadership workshop (see Section 3.2.3). Different SMEs working as chairs or convenors in SDOs were contacted to share their input and advice to SMEs wanting to get engaged in standardisation with leadership roles. The workshop attracted 51 registrants, with cooperation with other organisations or projects working with SMEs (Small Business Standards, NGI Sargasso). Another workshop dedicated to SMEs is planned in the second half of the project.
- **SME access to StandICT.eu2026 Training Modules:** Special training modules specifically targeted to SMEs have been created. The various training modules were regularly shared for information and feedback with the DIGITAL SMEs' community via social media or in presentations to its Working Group Standards (jointly held with Small Business Standards, the Annex III organisation mandated to represent SMEs in the European standardisation system). Such meetings were notably held on 4 May 2023, 15 September 2023, and 17 May 2024.
- **[SME Mentorship Programme](#):** For its Open Call 4, StandICT.eu launched a mentoring program to help SMEs navigate the world of ICT standardisation. This program pairs experienced standardisation experts with newcomers from SMEs to share their knowledge and offer guidance to these new experts. This system benefits both sides as SMEs gain valuable insights and experienced professionals can pass on their expertise, ensuring a solid foundation for future European standardisation efforts. The program aims to serve as a 'pull' lever towards other SMEs who may have previously been in doubt about getting involved in standardisation workstreams due to lack of expertise. 54 mentors and 22 mentees expressed their interest in the program for Open Call 4. At the

time of writing, these applicants have been paired based on shared topical expertise and interest, with 2-3 mentors for each mentee. An information session is planned before the summer of 2024 to get all of the mentors and mentees together and provide some overview of the next steps. The program is scheduled to be reconducted for each new Open Call, adapting to the lessons learnt from this initial pilot.

By working together on these three key steps, StandICT.eu can contribute to effectively bridging the gap in standardisation knowledge for SMEs. This will ultimately allow them to participate more actively in shaping future standards.

5. NEXT STEPS

Following the plan outlined by D4.1, an implementation plan has been developed to structure the organisation of webinars from Spring 2024 until the end of StandICT 2026 by the end of December 2025. Across the events that were organised, so far almost 800 experts registered.

In support of the success of these training events, we have relied on social media channels such as LinkedIn and X. Beyond these, the dissemination strategy requires the collaboration of contacts such as CEN-CENELEC, their national SDOs, ETSI, IEC, ISO, ITU, IEEE SA, and other ICT consortia. These joint efforts will allow the project to reach sufficient participants also for the future events.

Overall, finding potential outreach partners for StandICT2026's training activities is essential. These are some examples of potential partners and how to reach them:

- SMEs: Leverage partner DSME's membership in SBS to connect with SME communities.
- Open Source Communities: Partner with Open Forum Europe (OFE) to reach open source developers.
- Research Organisations: Explore collaboration with the European Association of Research and Technology Organisations (EARTO), representing over 350 Research and Technology organisations (RTOs) through Europe.
- Intellectual Property Offices: Investigate potential partnerships with the European Patent Office (EPO) and the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO) due to the link between patents and standards in some ICT fields.
- Standardisation Researchers and Educators: Partner with the European Academy for Standardisation (EURAS) to reach researchers and lecturers interested in standardisation.
- Industry Representatives: Use your existing contacts with national mirror committees and the HLF to leverage your industry connections and promote StandICT2026's training content and webinars.

For the second half of 2026, further webinars will address the geopolitics of ICT standardisation with a focus on China, but also Africa. Further topics will be the role of ICT standardisation and standards for start-ups. However, previous topics will be readdressed, e.g. on open source and patents reflecting ongoing developments.